

DAMAGE IDENTIFICATION AND APPLICATION OF PRESTRESSED CONCRETE BEAMS BASED ON HILBERT-HUANG TRANSFORM

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Abstract. In this paper, through the analysis of numerical and experimental studies with and without noise, the vibration characteristics of the prestressed concrete beam during failure process were studied. Runge-Kutta method was used to solve the partial differential equations of controlling vibration to obtain dynamic response under hammer excitation. The vibration characteristics of the test beam under different damage conditions were researched by Hilbert-Huang Transformation (HHT) time-frequency analysis method. Concrete strain, deflection and crack development, etc. were recorded during failure process, and dynamic testing of five key working conditions was made. The acceleration signals were obtained from each key condition and HHT was used to get instantaneous frequency-acceleration amplitude curve during each damage stage. The results showed that instantaneous frequency-acceleration amplitude curve obtained by the HHT can clearly reflect the degree of damage, the change of damage characteristic frequency display the extent of damage in the failure process.

Keywords: Prestressed concrete beam; Vibration analysis; Damage identification; Hilbert-huang transform; Experimental study

1. INTRODUCTION

Medium and Short span prestressed concrete bridge occupies a large proportion in Chinese highway Bridges. With the increase of traffic load and adverse effect of environment, there will be various forms of damage in the service, resulting in reduction of load carrying capacity of bridges. Therefore, it is of great practical significance to study the damage identification of medium and short span prestressed concrete structures.

The occurrence of structural damage will inevitably lead to the change of dynamic parameters of the structures, and the analysis of the signals obtained by the dynamic response of the structures is related to the accurate identification of the structure state [1]. Many scholars have successively carried out researches on damage identification of concrete beam structures by vibration test methods [2-8].

The traditional Fourier transform is to transform the signal from the time domain to information in the frequency domain, but it does not simultaneously possess the time-frequency resolution ability. The time-domain information will be lost in the transformation process. Wavelet transform is a signal processing method which has both time and frequency domain resolution. Wavelet analysis for engineering application problems exists in the choice of wavelet base. Analysis of the same question may produce different results by different wavelet base [9].

Hilbert-Huang Transform [10] (HHT) is a new time-frequency analysis method with self-adaptation, which can analyze both steady and non-stationary signals. This method firstly used the empirical mode decomposition (EMD) method to decompose the given signal adaptively step by step into the basic intrinsic mode function (IMF). The introduction of the decomposition method of signal local characteristics makes the concept of instantaneous frequency signal to become the real physical significance.

In this paper, the prestressed concrete hollow beam was taken as the research object, which had served for 11 years. It focused on the measurement of acceleration signals of constant prestressed concrete hollow beams with

different damage degrees under dynamic loads, as well as the signal processing and analysis of the changes of instantaneous frequency and acceleration amplitude of the hollow beam under time domain by using Hilbert-Huang transform, and explored the beam structural damage status and frequency changes of the damaged hollow beam after different static loads loading level.

2 HILBERT-HUANG TRANSFORMATION

Hilbert-Huang Transformation (HHT) consists of Huang transform and Hilbert spectrum analysis. The key of Huang transformation is empirical mode decomposition (EMD). EMD decomposes the signal into a sum of finite intrinsic mode functions (IMF). Any time series $x(t)$ can be expressed as the sum of n -order natural modal function (c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots) and a residual r_n after EMD decomposition.

$$x(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i + r_n \quad (1)$$

Every order component is a vibration modal with different amplitude and frequency, the first order modal function has the highest frequency. With the increase of the order number of modal its cycle become longer until close to a linear function of time. Hilbert transform gains the analytic signal of the signal through Hilbert transform to obtain the instantaneous frequency. All order modal functions $c_i(t)$ obtained by EMD decomposition were performed by Hilbert transformation, i. e. :

$$c_i(t) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int \frac{c_i(\tau)}{t - \tau} d\tau \quad (2)$$

The analytic signal $z_i(t)$ corresponding to $x(t)$ is:

$$z_i(t) = c_i(t) + jH[c_i(t)] = a_i(t) \exp[j\phi_i(t)] \quad (3)$$

Where: $a_i(t)$ and $\phi_i(t)$ is the amplitude function and phase function of the signal, respectively, as following formula.

$$a_i(t) = \sqrt{c_i^2(t) + H^2[c_i(t)]} \quad (4)$$

$$\phi_i(t) = \arctan\left(\frac{H[c_i(t)]}{c_i(t)}\right) \quad (5)$$

Further, the instantaneous frequency can be obtained:

$$\omega_i(t) = \frac{d\phi_i(t)}{dt} \quad (6)$$

$$f_i(t) = \frac{\omega_i(t)}{2\pi} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{d\phi_i(t)}{dt} \quad (7)$$

3 EXPERIMENT BACKGROUND

3.1 Dimensions and materials of test beam

Mid-span cross section and plan view of the PC experimental beam is shown in figure 1. The length of beam is 19.96 m, and calculation span is 19.30 m, ordinary reinforced configuration is $\Phi 8$, which adopts R235 hot rolled round steel bar. The prestressed steel strand is a high strength and low relaxation strand wire with standard strength 1860 MPa. The layout of steel strands is $8\Phi^{15.24} + 8\Phi^{15.24}$ with tension on both ends. The strength grade of concrete is C50.

Figure 1: Dimensions of the experimental beam

3.2 Test loading and test scheme

This test loading device select four sets of JAW-500A electro-hydraulic servo test system (500 kN). The two symmetrical loads are exerting on one-third points of the beam span determined by the calculation(As shown in figure 2). The live loading photo is shown in figure 3.

Figure 2: Loading diagram of the test beam (unit: cm)

Figure 3: The live loading photo

The deflection measurement points are arranged at the bottom of the beam in $L/4$, $L/2$ and $3L/4$ cross-sections of beam span and two sides of the two temporary supports respectively to measure the settlement or deflection in two end supports. At the same time, the deflection data are checked by steel ruler and wire-drawing displacement meter. Digital strain gauges along the top and bottom of the beam and sides web in the $L/4$, $L/2$, $3L/4$ cross-sections in longitudinal direction are arranged, steel strain gauges in the bottom bar area of the mid-span cross section of the beam are pasted to measure steel strains. The dynamic measurement adopts the acceleration sensors installed on the test beam gain correspond signal, as shown in the figure 4. vibration of the beam is stimulated by the test force hammer.

Figure 4: Layout of acceleration sensors

4 NUMERICAL CALCULATION OF VIBRATION CHARACTERISTICS OF TEST BEAM

4.1 Vibration partial differential equation of test beam

Figure 5 is a simply supported beam, and assume that the bending stiffness of the beam is $EI(x)$ and the mass of per beam length is $m(x)$, it can vary at any location x along the span L . The vertical load above the beam is $p(x,t)$, it can also vary with arbitrary location and time. The vertical displacement response of the beam is $v(x,t)$.

Considering the balance of all vertical forces:

$$V(x, t) + p(x, t)dx - [V(x, t) + \frac{\partial V(x, t)}{\partial x} dx] - m(x) \frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial t^2} dx - c(x) \frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial t} dx = 0 \quad (8)$$

Where $V(x, t)$ is the vertical force acting on the section, $m(x)dx \frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial t^2}$ is the resultant forces of transverse inertial forces acted on the micro segment, $c(x) \frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial t} dx$ is damping force acted on the micro segment, $c(x)$ is damping factor. The equation is divided by dx , we can get:

$$\frac{\partial V(x, t)}{\partial x} = p(x, t) - m(x) \frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial t^2} - c(x) \frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial t} \quad (9)$$

The second equilibrium equation can be obtained by summing the moment at the point on the elastic axis. When ignoring the second order moment term containing the inertial force and the applied load [11], we can get

$$M(x, t) + V(x, t)dx - [M(x, t) + \frac{\partial M(x, t)}{\partial x} dx] = 0 \quad (10)$$

Due to ignoring the moment of inertia, so have

$$\frac{\partial M(x, t)}{\partial x} = V(x, t) \quad (11)$$

Take the derivative of the above equation with respect to x , and replace it into Eq.(9)

$$\frac{\partial M^2(x, t)}{\partial x^2} + m(x) \frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial t^2} + c(x) \frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial t} = p(x, t) \quad (12)$$

The relationship between bending moment and curvature of beam is introduced

$$M(x, t) = EI(x) \left[\frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial x^2} \right] \quad (13)$$

Substitute Eq. (13) into Eq. (12), we can get:

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left\{ EI(x) \left[\frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial x^2} \right] \right\} + m(x) \frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial t^2} + c(x) \frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial t} = p(x, t) \quad (14)$$

Figure 5: Simply supported beam under dynamic loads

It is worth noting that the differential equation given by the Eq. (8) to Eq. (14) only shows the physical parameters such as the mass distribution, damping and bending stiffness of the beam that affect the vibration of a beam under an ideal perfect elastic body and the corresponding vibration displacement equation, which does not consider the influence of prestressing force within the beam. The cracking behavior of prestressed concrete beams under different static loads is only simply expressed by stiffness reduction. The dynamic signal obtained in the actual beam test has included the influence of the relevant physical parameters (such as the damage, cracking degree and the damping etc. of the beam). Theoretically, the magnitude of prestressing does have a certain influence on the vibration of the beam body, how to consider the effect of prestressing in vibration equation of the beam needs to be further studied and perfected in the future study. In this test process, it is assumed that the prestressing variation of the beam body is small and can be ignored.

4.2 Numerical calculation of dynamic response of test beam

In order to explore the feasibility of damage identification after the dynamic test signal of the test beam is decomposed into some basic intrinsic mode functions (IMF) by EMD, the displacement response signal of the concrete beam in actual constant prestressing is solved by numerical method, and then the relevant signal transformation is analyzed. When the stiffness, calculation span, mass and damping factor etc. parameters of test beam are substituted into the partial differential equation (14), taking the impact exciting load acted on the beam as 10 kN and the sampling frequency as 1000 Hz, the time-dependent displacement response of the beam can be calculated and gained during the 4s. The displacement response point is selected at the mid-span of the beam. As the damage of the structure will lead to the reduction of the beam bending stiffness, here the bending stiffness reduction of 5%, 10% and 15% for the beam is respectively defined to simulate the different damage cases of the beam. The dynamic response results at the mid-span point of test beam obtained by Runge-kutta method and Matlab programming according to Eq. (14) is shown in the figure 6.

The signal is decomposed by EMD, as shown in the figure 7. In order to eliminate the influence of endpoint effect when is decomposed by EMD, the intermediate data are selected for analysis, and the time-dependent curves of displacement amplitude and frequency are obtained, as shown in the figure 8.

Figure 6: Displacement response in the mid-span of test beam

Figure 9 shows the relationship curve of the instantaneous frequency-time of the test beam in different degrees of damage. As you can see, the instantaneous frequency beam fluctuates up and down near the base frequency. With deepening of the damage degree, the instantaneous frequency range becomes lower, which can reflect the extent of the damage. It shows that the index is an effective indicator to measure the damage degree of structure.

Figure 7: EMD of mid-span displacement response

Figure 8: Time-dependent curve of instantaneous amplitude and frequency

Figure 9: Instantaneous frequency-time relation curves in different damage states

5 TEST CONTENT AND DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 Test process

The whole static loading process of the test beam is divided into 18 stages, mainly including loading before cracking, stage after cracking, stage near 90% ultimate load and the failure stage of the test beam. The holding time of each stage remains around 15mins after loading. After the displacement meter reading and crack development are basically stable, the crack development of the beam is observed and recorded. After collecting the displacement meter and strain gauge readings, unload to zero. The experiment shows that when the test load is up to 200 kN, the concrete on the top of the beam flange crushes, and the crack width of the beam increases obviously. The crack distribution in the limit state of the structure is shown in the figure 10. The crack development in the key stages of the whole test process is listed in table 1.

The corresponding dynamic response is also tested in five key stages by the hammer exciting load acted on at the mid-span of the beam, which mainly include the Condition I : he initial state of beam; Condition II : unloading after the load reaches 90 kN (test beam is just cracking); Condition III: unloading after the load reaches 155 kN (ordinary steel bar has begun to yield); Condition IV: unloading after the load reaches 185 kN (crack width is more than 1 mm); Condition V : loading up to the ultimate load of test beam(200 kN).

Figure 10: Crack diagram of test beam in ultimate state

Table 1. Crack development in the key stages of the whole test process

Load value (kN)	Maximum crack width (mm)	Fracture depth extension (depth of beam $h=90\text{cm}$)	Crack development description
0	0	0	No cracks
90	0.02	0.01h	The width of cracks is small for the bottom plate near the mid-span
125	0.2	0.5h	The cracks extend to half beam depth, and transverse cracks appear on the bottom plate
155	0.3	0.65h	Cracks appear in the whole area from the quarter point to the middle of the span, and the cracks continue to develop
185	1.0	0.85h	The crack depth extends to the lower edge of top slab of test beam, and the crack width is more than 1mm
200	2.8	h	Several cracks near the mid-span section is more than 2.5mm wide, the maximum is up to 2.8mm. The concrete in top flange of the beam near mid-span is crushed

5.2 Test data analysis

The actual measurement of the acceleration signal will inevitably encounter noise interference. Before loading, the acceleration response in mid-span measured by the test is shown in figure 11. The response signal is decomposed by EMD, and the results are shown in figure 12.

Figure 11: Acceleration response in the mid-span of the test beam

Figure 12: Results of the acceleration response decomposed by EMD

When acceleration signal gained in the different conditions is transformed by HHT, we can get instantaneous frequency-time curves and acceleration amplitude-time curves. After removing the effect of endpoints, the instantaneous frequency-time curves and acceleration amplitude-time curves are analyzed within the range of 1.0~3.0s.

The instantaneous frequency and amplitude are one by one corresponding through the time scale, the instantaneous frequency-acceleration amplitude curves are made in the different conditions, as shown in figure 13. The loss rate of base characteristic frequency of damaged beam is corresponding to the applied load, as drawn in figure 14.

Figure 13: The instantaneous frequency-acceleration amplitude curve of the test beam in each damaged state

Figure 14: Loss rate of base frequencies of damaged beam corresponding to different loading levels

It is found that from figure 14, the loss rate of base characteristic frequency of the beam reflects the damage degree and corresponded to the loading level. At the same time, it reflects the change of base frequency of damaged beam in different damage conditions. HHT transformation can clearly display the damage degree of test beam.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, vibration characteristics of existing prestressed concrete beams with and without noise are respectively analyzed by the numerical calculation and experimentally investigated. The following conclusions are drawn:

- The vibration partial differential equation of test beam solved by the Runge-kutta method is proposed. The dynamic response signal of simulated beam obtained under the hammer excitation force is analyzed by HHT in time-frequency domain. The vibration characteristics of the test beam are described in different damage conditions. The results show that the time history of instantaneous frequency variation obtained by HHT can reflect the occurrence and degree of damage in the structural system.
- In terms of the acceleration signal obtained by the HHT transformation in different cases, the instantaneous frequency-acceleration amplitude curves of the beam have been obtained during the damage process. It is found that the loss rate of characteristic frequency of damaged beam reflects the damage degree and corresponds to the loading level. It also reflects the change of damage characteristic frequency under in different damage conditions. HHT transformation can clearly display and predict the damage degree of test beam.

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